

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: O'Bleness****FIRST NAME: Michael****PROGRAM CODE: DBIO****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 11)

List of Key Concepts:

1. Construct of the academic essay (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 8-12)
2. Making a successful argument (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 13-14)
3. Punctuation matters (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 16-23)
4. Differentiating US vs UK contextual language (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 25-32)
5. Style for clarity, consistency & cohesiveness (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 41-64)
6. Finally, plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 34-39)

THE CREATIVE PROCESS OF CONSTRUCTING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

Improving my academic writing continues to be foundational to my continued academic pursuit. Academia has been in my blood since I began earnestly in the mid-1980s, obtaining my undergraduate degrees in psychology and nursing. This was followed by a Master's degree in Business Administration, Master of Nursing, and post-graduate studies in nursing. Enrolment in Euler's Doctor of Bio and Clinical Ethics presents new challenges. Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024 present a roadmap that creates a measured pathway and sets expectations for effective academic writing. I intend to incorporate my past experiences with the insights, guidance, and expertise of the Euler faculty. It has been stated that academic writing has a level of formality where evidence is presented, answering the presupposition of a hypothesis (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 34-39). This melding of inquisitiveness and the rigor of research are, for me, the breath I take. I admit to a mild level of trepidation as I begin this phase of my academic career. It is with honor that I will undertake this challenge.

2) THE CONSTRUCT OF THE ACADEMIC ESSAY

Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024 have formulated a hierarchical scheme that is not unlike Maslow's hierarchy of human needs. The foundation from which all other levels of academic essay writing flow is an analysis of questions and keying in terminology. Today's question is to present an individualized analysis in a first-person experiential narrative of the content contained in the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack (Period 1). How do I answer this initial question? Through reading and researching the topic. This is second nature, as I have immersed myself in lifelong learning and questioning. As I organize my thoughts on approaching this task, I envision where I will draw from to formulate my responses and identify specific decision points (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 14). In constructing a rough draft, I will begin initial refinements and editing, frequently letting my mind percolate what I have produced for a while. At my disposal are several tools, from Grammarly,¹ the Turabian manual for academic writers/researchers², and Zotero³ combined to enhance and improve my writing experience. It is paramount in academic writing to organize, present, argue, and defend (in writing and orally) a particular position, idea, or hypothesis. It is to this end that presenting a cogent, cohesive, well-written paper is an orchestrated process (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 8-12).

One final thought on constructing an academic essay addressing clarity: I would be remiss if I did not examine how the use, misuse, or omission of appropriate punctuation can guide, mislead, or confuse the reader. This has always followed me throughout my academic and personal writing: the use or overuse of the dreaded comma. I tend to overthink it. I also will admit that I continue to insert appropriate punctuation where I believe it belongs, but I am grateful for editing software. "Academic essays seek to provide an answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence." (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 7). It is this one element 'to communicate' that the misuse of punctuation is no less critical than the misuse of grammar. I believe effective writing hinges on both grammar and punctuation.

3) MAKING A SUCCESSFUL ARGUMENT

I will argue that Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024 have constructed an effective document outlining the use of formal style in writing an academic essay. A counter-argument would emphasize that for the creative writer, this is an innate quality that does

¹ Which is an invaluable aid in keeping my writing on track, correcting grammar, punctuation, etc.

² Turabian provides me with excellent direction on constructing a thesis and producing a dissertation. It is an extension of the Chicago Manual of Style. I am vaguely familiar with as most of my academic writing follows the American Psychological Association (APA) manual of style. It is of note that Turabian references APA for formatting tables.

³ Tracking and documenting references is daunting I am appreciative of having Zotero available to manage this aspect of my writing.

not necessitate a scripted style, although this may prove troubling (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 41). Their approach has given me pause for thought and confirmed my notion of what it takes to construct an effective essay. Central to an essay is positing an argument and effectively defending the proposal. The intent of constructing an argument (or thesis) is well-managed by focusing on a specific issue, problem, or idea. Also, do not over-generalize, realizing that coverage of a topic that is too broad may lose the attention of your audience and weaken the strength of your original argument. Clarity of writing is as important as being concise.⁴ There is clarity of thought that can begin to meander again, muddying my original point. I must disclose that I am often guilty of attempting to use language and words that are esoteric or more elaborate than necessary. I am not sure which may become too boring to the reader, such as my use of neologisms or aimless rantings when I stray from the intended focus of my argument. In supporting my argument, I consider the use of direct quotes as a necessary tool (evil) and strive to limit them. However, direct quotes used judiciously can add that level of authority to my argument. One additional thought. The ability to recognize alternate points of view is crucial to authentically representing an argument. Acknowledging views contrary to my stated premise gives the reader insight into how I have developed my rationale (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 13-14).

4) DIFFERENTIATING US VS UK CONTEXTUAL LANGUAGE

I am beginning to appreciate the implications of studying at an international level. It was not a part of my academic experiences to date having to consider a stylistic approach to how my writing might read to an audience of diverse nationalities and their exposure to very distinct styles of English. This presents an opportunity to appreciate the variation between Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE), knowing that I need to be aware of how I or another audience might interpret a particular passage. "American and British English are both variants of World English. As such, they are more similar than different, especially with "educated" or "scientific" English. Most divergence can be ascribed to differing national histories and cultural development..." (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 25). There are some variances that have become part of my lexicon, such as 'bonnet' (SBE) referring to the 'hood' (SAE) of a car. Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024 have introduced an assortment of variations and similarities in SAE and SBE regarding topics of pronunciation, spelling, meaning, and general usage of grammar, syntax, and punctuation. The use of language and the context in which it is presented at times are taken for granted. This is especially relevant because each profession has its own jargon, making outsiders feel disenfranchised.⁵ Words matter, and I am consistently and consciously aware

⁴ Throughout my academic endeavors, the ability to construct and present an argument, response, or idea has often been restricted by total word count, forcing clarity and conciseness.

⁵ I can recall an event in the operating room where MD's and RN's have their own jargon and means of shortcutting verbal communication a patient heard 1 and 25 and expressed their concern as 'do I only have a

of other's perceptions of what I said and what I intend to convey. Additionally, colloquial terms may be specific to a culture. What terms are used colloquially among members of a specific group or ethnically identifiable subset of a community may not be appropriate for general use in conversation by nonmembers. This is especially relevant to terms that are generally recognized as racial epithets (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 29-31).

5) STYLE FOR CLARITY, CONSISTENCY & COHESIVENESS

I have touched on style in some of my previous responses, such as the use of a hierarchical scheme in delineating the steps in constructing an academic essay. Easily, the use of a particular style can affect the formation of an argument, maintaining clarity and conciseness in presenting a position. It is also argued that formatted style can be seen as a hindrance in the creative process of writing. Free-form creative writing in fields where technical information is to be presented without ambiguity would lend itself to a patchwork that only the original author may interpret meaning. Having used the APA manual of style for nearly four decades, I appreciate how style has made reading and creating documents an essential part of academia. "The use of punctuation and correct grammar is well established and clear, but the style is much more than just the correct usage of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary" (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 41). For me, the use of a manual of style is an element of practice providing the structure for effectively presenting cogent and coherent arguments, concepts, and technical information to a wide audience. The Turabian Manual of Style is an extension of the Chicago Manual of Style directed specifically to guide the construction of post-graduate research, theses, and dissertations. I already have an appreciation for the author's approach to compartmentalizing and deconstructing the process of formulating a thesis and writing the dissertation. I also appreciate Cleenewerck & Gulma's inclusion of a 'crib sheet' as I tend to use page tabs to locate stylistic references easily. This is an added convenience, as is the addition of Latin abbreviations and expressions in chapter seven (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 59-64).

6) FINALLY, PLAGIARISM

I cannot recall a time since high school when the intentional use of someone else work was wrong in life in general but has exceptionally specific standards within the academic arena. The use of others' work without citing credit or the intentional use of another's work without crediting the originating author is an ethical breach of conduct. This ethical standard is a universal standard where any publication in the public domain is subject to scrutinization and held accountable for upholding this concept of acknowledging due credit. Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024 define plagiarism as:

I in 25 chance?' When the reality of this expression was meant only for the MD and the RN as a procedural order.

Taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper for you and then putting [sic] your name on it and giving [sic] it to your professor would be plagiarism.

I have cultivated a practice of avoiding plagiarism through practicing paraphrasing and, when in doubt, citing. The art of paraphrasing is a honed skill, and with applications such as Grammarly and Turnitin, an author's writing can be indexed and scored, resulting in a similarity index. Within specified parameters such as 15% similarity, an author can be relatively confident in a) proper citations and b) adequate paraphrasing and originality (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 34-37).

7) CONCLUSION

As I consider What academic writing means to me and how to achieve the level of excellence needed to compete at the post-graduate level, I am heartened by the success I have achieved and the opportunity to expand my endeavors. Cleenewerck & Gulma's ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack (Period 1) provides guidance in academic essay writing and a basis for developing proficiency in producing quality, cohesive, and cogent responses, reports, and research. One of the strengths these authors helped me focus on is the hierarchical approach to constructing an effective essay. It can be easily said that making a convincing argument is a crucial element in the formulation of one's position. Additionally, without a manual of style consistency, readability, and usage of language, only a few would gain any benefit from trying to interpret an author's intent. As a final thought, it remains incumbent on the author to understand what plagiarism is and the implications for maintaining academic standards. I have enjoyed exploring the material contained in this assignment and the practical application it will have on my academic writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.